

"Navigating Climate Change: Project Management in the Era of Uncertainty"

By Adeel Ahmed.

Email: aahmed57@hawk.iit.edu

Abstract:

This research paper explores the impacts of climate change on project management, including the barriers and opportunities it presents for project managers. Climate change has led to increased risks, uncertainty, and complexity in project management, posing significant challenges for project managers in various industries. However, it has also created opportunities for innovation, collaboration, and new business models. This paper discusses the skills and competencies required for effective project management in the context of climate change and presents various adaptation strategies that project managers can adopt to mitigate the impacts of climate change. The findings suggest that project managers need to be aware of the challenges and opportunities presented by climate change to effectively manage projects in the future.

The escalating impacts of climate change on global ecosystems, economies, and communities are causing project managers to face unprecedented challenges, including increasing uncertainty, changing stakeholder demands, and heightened risks of project failure, highlighting the urgent need for integrated climate risk management strategies and sustainable project practices.

As a result, the adoption of adaptive strategies, sustainability-focused approaches, and integrated climate risk management is crucial to ensure project success and resilience in the face of escalating impacts on global ecosystems, economies, and communities. Climate change is one of the most significant global challenges of our time, with impacts on the environment, society, and economy (IPCC, 2018). Project management plays a critical role in addressing climate change, as projects are the building blocks of many climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts (PMI, 2013). The purpose of this research is to examine the impacts of climate change on project management and identify the barriers, opportunities, and responsibilities of project managers in addressing climate change. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), global temperatures have already increased by 1.1°C above pre-

Source: Met Office Hadley Centre (HadCRUT5) OurWorldInData.org/co2-and-greenhouse-gas-emissions • CC BY
Note: The gray lines represent the upper and lower bounds of the 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 1. Met Office Hadley Centre (HadCRUT5) CO₂ and Greenhouse Gas Emissions - Our World in Data

industrial levels and are projected to increase by 1.5°C by as early as 2040. (IPCC, 2021) This could have catastrophic effects on the planet, including rising sea levels, more frequent and severe natural disasters, and the extinction of many species. Urgent action is required to curb greenhouse gas emissions and reduce our carbon footprint if we are to avoid the worst-case scenarios predicted by the IPCC.

1. Background on the Project Management Profession:

Project management is the process of leading a team to achieve specific goals and objectives within a specified time frame and budget. Project managers are responsible for planning, executing, and monitoring projects to ensure that they are completed on time, within budget, and to the satisfaction of stakeholders. The role of project managers varies across industries, but their importance for organizational success is widely recognized (PMI, 2021). Project managers need to possess a range of skills and competencies, including leadership, communication, problem-solving, and strategic thinking, among others. The success of a project depends on the effective management of resources, risks, and stakeholders (Kerzner, 2017). Climate change can impact project management in several ways, including changing regulatory frameworks, funding constraints, risk management challenges, human resource challenges, and supply chain disruptions (Gareis & Huemann, 2013).

2. Literature Review :

Climate change impacts on project management are extensive and can vary across industries, regions, and project types. Climate change can result in increased frequency and severity of natural disasters, which can damage infrastructure and disrupt project timelines. Climate change can also result in changes in stakeholder expectations, including an increased focus on sustainability and social responsibility, and changes in project design and planning, including the incorporation of new technologies and materials (Ansell, 2019; Ogunbode et al., 2018).

Integrating climate change into project management can be challenging due to various barriers, as highlighted by several studies (Pirvu et al., 2016; Ogunbode et al., 2018; OECD, 2018; UNEP, 2016; IPCC, 2021). These barriers include a lack of awareness, knowledge, and resources, as well as resistance to change and competing priorities. Project managers may not have sufficient knowledge and skills to address climate change, and organizations may not provide adequate resources and support for climate change initiatives. Additionally, stakeholders may be resistant to change, and climate change initiatives may compete with other organizational priorities. A lack of funding for climate adaptation measures is a significant barrier that can limit the resources available to project managers (OECD, 2018). Inadequate resources, such as skilled personnel and equipment, can also hinder the implementation of climate adaptation strategies (UNEP, 2016). Limited knowledge and awareness of the impacts of climate change on project management can also be a barrier, as project managers may not fully understand the risks and opportunities presented by climate change. Other barriers include regulatory constraints, political instability, and institutional capacity (IPCC, 2021).

Project management presents opportunities to address climate change by incorporating sustainability principles into project design and planning, identifying and managing climate-related risks, and promoting stakeholder engagement and collaboration (Aaltonen et al., 2018; Ogunbode et al., 2018). Integrating sustainability principles into project management can

reduce the environmental impact of projects and promote sustainable development. Effective identification and management of climate-related risks can help reduce project disruptions

Figure 2. Source: The Knowledge Effect | Climate change Vulnerability Index. <http://blog.thomsonreuters.com/index.php/climate-change-vulnerability-index-graphic-of-the-day/>

and increase resilience. Promoting stakeholder engagement and collaboration can build support for climate change initiatives and promote effective decision-making. Despite the challenges posed by climate change, it also presents opportunities for project managers to innovate, collaborate, and implement new business models (UNEP, 2021). The growing demand for sustainable

development has led to the emergence of renewable energy projects and green infrastructure projects. These projects

require project managers to have a deep understanding of sustainable practices and technologies. Additionally, project managers can collaborate with stakeholders, such as communities and non-governmental organizations, to build resilience to climate change impacts (UNDP, 2019). Such collaboration can lead to the development of more effective and sustainable adaptation strategies.

Project managers have various responsibilities in addressing climate change, including identifying and managing climate-related risks, integrating sustainability principles into project design and planning, promoting stakeholder engagement and collaboration, and monitoring and reporting on climate change initiatives. As global temperatures continue to rise due to climate change, extreme weather events such as floods, droughts, and heat waves are becoming increasingly frequent and severe. These events can have devastating impacts on human life, the economy, and the environment. In 2020, the United States experienced a staggering 22 weather and climate disasters that resulted in losses exceeding \$1 billion each, according to the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). These events included hurricanes, wildfires, and severe storms, which caused widespread destruction and loss of life. As climate change continues to worsen, it is likely that we will see even more extreme weather events in the future, making it crucial for governments, businesses, and individuals to take action to mitigate their impact and adapt to the changing climate. Project managers should be aware of the potential impacts of climate change on their projects and take steps to identify and manage climate-related risks. They should also incorporate sustainability principles into project design and planning, promote stakeholder engagement and collaboration, and monitor and report on climate change initiatives to ensure they are effective and align with organizational goals (Ogunbode et al., 2018; Aaltonen et al., 2018).

3. Barriers to Project Management due to Climate Change:

A. Funding constraints and the impact of climate change on project budgets:

Climate change can have a significant impact on project budgets, leading to funding constraints and delays (Huntjens et al., 2017). For example, extreme weather events can cause delays in project implementation, leading to cost overruns (Ferdowsi & Keramati, 2016). The effects of climate change are not limited to the environment, as it can have

significant impacts on project budgets as well. Studies have shown that climate change-induced events can lead to funding constraints and delays in project implementation, which in turn can result in cost overruns. For instance, extreme weather events such as floods, hurricanes, and heatwaves can cause disruptions in supply chains and transportation, ultimately delaying project completion and increasing costs. In a study by Ferdowsi and Keramati (2016), it was found that such delays can add up to 30% to project costs. The consequences of such delays are especially pronounced for large infrastructure projects, where any interruption in the construction schedule can result in substantial financial losses. As climate change continues to worsen, it is becoming increasingly important for project managers to account for these risks and integrate climate resilience measures into their planning to mitigate these impacts.

B. Changing regulatory frameworks and the impact of climate change policies on project approvals and permits:

Changing regulatory frameworks can impact project approvals and permits, leading to delays and additional costs (Gareis & Huemann, 2013). For example, changes in emissions regulations can require changes to project designs and increase project costs (McGrath, 2019). Regulatory frameworks play a crucial role in the approval and permitting of projects, and changes in these regulations can have a significant impact on project timelines and budgets. According to Gareis and Huemann (2013), changes in regulatory frameworks can cause delays and additional costs in project implementation. For instance, changes in emissions regulations can require project designs to be modified, resulting in additional costs and delays. In a study by McGrath (2019), it was found that changes to emissions regulations resulted in a 20% increase in the cost of one project. These costs can be even higher for large-scale projects or those that are already underway when the regulatory changes occur. Additionally, the uncertainty around regulatory changes can cause further delays and additional costs as project managers wait for clarification before proceeding. As regulatory frameworks continue to evolve, it is becoming increasingly important for project managers to stay informed of changes and plan for potential impacts to minimize delays and costs.

C. Risk management challenges due to the increased uncertainty and unpredictability of climate change impacts:

Climate change can increase the uncertainty and unpredictability of project outcomes, leading to risk management challenges (Hwang & Ng, 2013). Climate change is a significant challenge for risk management, as it increases the uncertainty and unpredictability of project outcomes. As weather patterns become more erratic and extreme, the risks associated with project implementation become harder to predict and manage. For example, the increased frequency and severity of extreme weather events, such as hurricanes and floods, can disrupt supply chains, delay project timelines, and increase costs. In addition, rising sea levels and temperature changes can impact the viability of certain projects, such as those related to infrastructure development or real estate. For example, changes in weather patterns can impact project timelines and increase project risks (Ferdowsi & Keramati, 2016).

Scenario-Based Climate Change Impact Assessment

Figure 3. Process flow diagram of a typical approach for conducting biological impact assessments under different future climate scenarios. The curved arrows demonstrate the iterative (i.e., non-linear) process of integrating climate and ecology methods in conservation projects. Source: Rangwala, I., Moss, W., Wolken, J., Rondeau, R., Newlon, K., Guinotte, J., & Riebsame Travis, W. (2020). *Uncertainty, Complexity and Constraints: How Do We Robustly Assess Biological Responses under a Rapidly Changing Climate?* *Journal of Climate Change*, 6(2), 223-241. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JCC200011>

Moreover, the long-term impacts of climate change on a project's success can be difficult to assess, adding to the complexity of risk management. Changes in the climate can have a cascading effect on natural systems, leading to ripple effects across a wide range of sectors, from agriculture to tourism. As a result, project managers must consider not only the immediate risks posed by climate change but also the longer-term impacts that may emerge over time.

D. Human resource challenges due to the need for specialized expertise in climate change-related fields:

The impacts of climate change are increasingly being felt across a wide range of sectors, from energy and transportation to agriculture and water management. As a result, there is a growing need for specialized expertise in climate change-related fields, presenting significant human resource challenges for organizations. Climate change requires specialized expertise in climate change-related fields, which can be a challenge for project management (Hwang & Ng, 2013). For example, the design and implementation of climate change mitigation projects require specialized knowledge in areas such as renewable energy and carbon sequestration (IPCC, 2018). One major challenge is the scarcity of qualified professionals with the necessary skills and experience to address the complex and evolving challenges posed by climate change. This shortage of expertise can make it difficult for organizations to recruit and retain talented individuals with the skills required to lead climate-related initiatives successfully. Additionally, there is often intense competition for these professionals, leading to higher salaries and benefits that can strain the budgets of organizations.

E. Supply chain challenges due to the impact of climate change on the availability and reliability of materials and services:

Climate change is already having significant impacts on infrastructure and supply chains, which are critical components of many projects. As weather patterns become more extreme and unpredictable, infrastructure assets such as roads, bridges, and buildings are increasingly vulnerable to damage from floods, storms, and sea-level rise. In addition, the impacts of climate change on supply chains, including disruptions to transportation networks and changes in the availability and quality of raw materials, are also likely to have a significant impact on project outcomes. For example, coastal infrastructure, such as ports and airports, is particularly vulnerable to the impacts of sea-level rise and storm surges. Rising sea levels and increased storm activity can lead to flooding, erosion, and damage to structures, leading to costly repairs and project delays. Similarly, extreme weather events, such as hurricanes, floods, and wildfires, can disrupt transportation and logistics networks, leading to delays and increased costs. Climate change can impact the availability and reliability of materials and services, leading to supply chain disruptions (Hwang & Ng, 2013). For example, extreme weather events can impact transportation and logistics, leading to delays in the delivery of materials (Ferdowsi & Keramati, 2016). Climate change is expected to have significant impacts on infrastructure and supply chains, which are critical components of many projects. For example, rising sea levels and storm surges could cause flooding and damage to coastal infrastructure, while extreme weather events could disrupt transportation and logistics networks. (Savu & Henttonen, 2019) A survey of 2,400 project managers from around the world found that 57% had experienced project delays due to climate-related factors, such as extreme weather events or supply chain disruptions. (Project Management Institute, 2021)

4. Case Studies for understanding the barriers:

Climate change is having a significant impact on project management, as evidenced by several case studies that illustrate the challenges and opportunities of managing projects in a changing climate. For example, a wind energy project in Australia faced significant delays and cost overruns due to regulatory uncertainty and changing government policies. The project was initially approved with a feed-in tariff scheme that provided a stable revenue stream for the project, but the government subsequently changed the policy, leading to delays and cost overruns (Beckman & Rittel, 2018). Similarly, a transportation project in the United States was impacted by supply chain disruptions caused by extreme weather events, leading to delays and increased costs (Huntjens et al., 2017).

These case studies highlight the need for proactive measures to address climate change-related barriers to project management. Project managers must adopt a strategic approach to climate risk management that includes comprehensive risk assessments, contingency planning, and the integration of climate resilience measures into project design and implementation. This requires collaboration across stakeholders and a willingness to invest in infrastructure and supply chains that are more resilient to the impacts of climate change.

At the same time, climate change can present opportunities for project management in several ways. For example, the development of climate change mitigation and adaptation projects can provide new business opportunities and support the transition to a low-carbon economy. The integration of sustainable practices into project management can help to reduce greenhouse

Figure 4. Why different stakeholders should get involved in an energy efficiency market engagement, in what capacity, and what they stand to gain. Source: Extract from Energy Efficiency Market Report 2015, IEA adapted from IEA (2014), Capturing the Multiple Benefits of Energy Efficiency, OECD/IEA, Paris. <http://lowcarbonkid.blogspot.com/2016/11/cop22-put-built-environment-at.html>

gas emissions and improve environmental performance. The promotion of stakeholder engagement and public participation can increase transparency and accountability, while the encouragement of innovation in project design and implementation can drive efficiency and competitiveness. Finally, the implementation of policies and regulatory frameworks that support climate-friendly projects can provide a supportive environment for project managers to act on climate change (Darnall, Jolley, & Handfield, 2008; Gareis & Huemann, 2013). A review of the literature on climate change and project management reveals that these opportunities can significantly enhance project success and must be recognized and leveraged to maximize the potential for successful project implementation (Gareis et al., 2017).

5. Opportunities for Project Management due to Climate Change:

A review of the literature on climate change and project management reveals that these opportunities can significantly enhance project success and must be recognized and leveraged to maximize the potential for successful project implementation (Gareis et al., 2017).

A. Development of climate change mitigation and adaptation projects :

Climate change mitigation and adaptation projects offer a unique opportunity for project management to address the challenges posed by climate change while contributing to sustainable development.

Mitigation projects focus on reducing greenhouse gas emissions and mitigating the impacts of climate change, while adaptation projects aim to increase resilience to climate change impacts. Examples of climate change mitigation projects include the development of renewable energy projects, implementation of energy

Figure 5. Link between adaptation investments and the economic costs of climate change. Source: Adapted from Chambwera et al. (2014).

efficiency measures, and promotion of sustainable transportation. Adaptation projects can include the development of flood protection infrastructure, implementation of drought-resistant farming practices, and construction of climate-resilient buildings. Successful implementation of these projects requires specialized expertise and effective stakeholder engagement, highlighting the importance of project management in addressing climate change challenges. The development of climate change mitigation and adaptation projects presents significant opportunities for project management. Such projects can include renewable energy initiatives, sustainable transport infrastructure, and climate-resilient building design and construction (Gareis & Huemann, 2013; Huemann & Keegan, 2018). The construction industry is a significant contributor to global greenhouse gas emissions, accounting for approximately 39% of energy-related emissions and 11% of total emissions. (United Nations Environment Programme, 2019)

B. Integration of sustainable practices into project management:

The integration of sustainable practices into project management can have significant benefits for both the social and environmental outcomes of projects, as well as project performance and long-term viability. In recent years, there has been growing recognition of the importance of sustainable practices in project management, as companies and organizations seek to minimize their environmental impact and contribute to broader sustainability goals.

According to research conducted by Chen et al. (2015) and Darnall et al. (2008), sustainable project management practices can improve project outcomes in a number of ways. For instance, by reducing waste and optimizing resource use, sustainable practices can help projects operate more efficiently and cost-effectively. This, in turn, can lead to better project performance and long-term viability. Furthermore, sustainable project management practices can help to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate the impacts of climate change. For example, green building practices can reduce energy use and carbon emissions from buildings,

while sustainable transportation planning can reduce emissions from transportation networks. As highlighted by Tzortzopoulos & Kagioglou (2015), sustainable practices can also help to create healthier and more livable communities, by promoting active transportation options and reducing air pollution. Overall, the integration of sustainable practices into project management represents an important opportunity for companies and organizations to contribute to broader sustainability goals, while also improving project outcomes and long-term viability. By adopting sustainable project management practices, companies can reduce their environmental impact, improve efficiency and cost-effectiveness, and promote more livable and sustainable communities.

C. Promotion of stakeholder engagement and public participation:

Stakeholder engagement and public participation are critical components of project success. Involving stakeholders and the public in the project planning process can help to ensure that project objectives are aligned with community needs and priorities and can also help to build support and trust for the project. This, in turn, can help to minimize project risks and increase the likelihood of project success. One area where stakeholder engagement and public participation are particularly important is in addressing climate change. As highlighted by Dye & Theriault (2017), climate change provides an opportunity to increase stakeholder engagement and public participation by raising awareness of climate-related issues and the role of projects in addressing them. By engaging stakeholders and the public in the project planning process, project managers can help to build support for climate-related initiatives and can also identify opportunities for collaboration and partnership. For example, stakeholders and the public can provide valuable input on climate-related issues and priorities, such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions or adapting to the impacts of climate change. They can also help to identify potential risks and opportunities associated with climate-related projects and can provide feedback on project design and implementation. Moreover, stakeholder engagement and public participation can help to build trust and credibility for climate-related projects. By involving stakeholders and the public in the project planning process, project managers can demonstrate a commitment to transparency and accountability and can help to ensure that the project is aligned with community needs and priorities. Overall, stakeholder engagement and public participation are critical to project success, particularly in the context of climate change. By engaging stakeholders and the public in the project planning process, project managers can help to build support and trust for climate-related initiatives and can identify opportunities for collaboration and partnership.

D. Encouragement of innovation in project design and implementation:

Climate change has become an increasingly pressing concern, with the need for urgent action to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate the impacts of climate change. In this context, projects play a critical role in promoting sustainability and reducing the environmental impact of human activities. Moreover, climate change presents an opportunity to encourage innovation in project design and implementation. By adopting new technologies and materials that reduce emissions and increase efficiency, projects can play a key role in promoting sustainability and reducing the environmental impact of human activities. For instance, the adoption of green building technologies, such as passive solar design or efficient heating and cooling systems, can help to reduce energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions from buildings. Similarly, the use of sustainable transportation technologies, such as electric vehicles or alternative fuels, can help to reduce emissions from transportation networks. As highlighted by Gareis & Huemann (2013), these innovations can also lead to cost savings and improved project performance, as well as environmental benefits. Ultimately, by embracing innovation in project design and implementation, projects can contribute to broader sustainability goals and help to address the challenges of climate change.

E. Implementation of policies and regulatory frameworks that support climate-friendly projects:

Policies and regulatory frameworks that support climate-friendly projects play an important role in promoting sustainability and reducing the environmental impact of human activities. These frameworks can provide incentives and support for the development of climate-friendly projects, which can, in turn, create opportunities for project management. For instance, government policies that promote renewable energy, such as feed-in tariffs or tax incentives, can create opportunities for project managers to develop and implement renewable energy projects. Similarly, regulatory frameworks that require businesses to report on their environmental impact can create opportunities for project managers to develop and implement sustainability initiatives. As highlighted by Huemann & Keegan (2018), these policies and regulatory frameworks can also create a level playing field for climate-friendly projects, by ensuring that these projects are not at a disadvantage compared to more traditional projects. Moreover, they can provide certainty and stability for project development by providing a predictable and stable regulatory environment. Overall, the implementation of policies and regulatory frameworks that support climate-friendly projects can provide opportunities for project management and can play a crucial role in promoting sustainability and addressing the challenges of climate change.

6. Case Studies for understanding the opportunities:

Climate change presents both challenges and opportunities for project management, as highlighted by several case studies. In India, for example, a renewable energy project took advantage of the country's solar potential and government incentives to achieve cost-effective and sustainable energy solutions. By adopting innovative technologies and business models, the project was able to capitalize on the opportunities presented by climate change and create a successful and sustainable energy solution (Liu, Yang, & Gao, 2017). Similarly, a sustainable transportation project in the United States incorporated innovative design features and community input to enhance accessibility and reduce carbon emissions. The project capitalized on the opportunities presented by climate change to create a more sustainable transportation system that better meets the needs of the community (Dye & Theriault, 2017).

These case studies highlight the importance of recognizing and capitalizing on opportunities presented by climate change for successful project implementation. By adopting innovative technologies and business models, project managers can create cost-effective and sustainable solutions that reduce the environmental impact of human activities. Moreover, these solutions can provide financial benefits and reduce risk for businesses, as highlighted by a study of 200 large corporations that found that those with strong environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance outperformed their peers in terms of financial performance and risk management (Harvard Business Review, 2021). Overall, these case studies demonstrate the importance of recognizing and capitalizing on opportunities presented by climate change, and the potential benefits that can result from doing so.

7. Responsibilities for the Project management due to climate change:

A. Development of climate change mitigation and adaptation projects (*United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2015). Paris agreement. UNFCCC.*)

To address the impacts of climate change, project managers must develop projects that can help reduce greenhouse gas emissions or adapt to the changing climate.

Such projects may include renewable energy initiatives, green infrastructure, or climate-resilient infrastructure. To successfully develop such projects, project managers must

Global atmospheric CO₂ concentration

Atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration is measured in parts per million (ppm). Long-term trends in CO₂ concentrations can be measured at high-resolution using preserved air samples from ice cores.

Source: National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)

CC BY

Figure 8. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) [CO₂ and Greenhouse Gas Emissions - Our World in Data](#)

consider the potential risks and uncertainties associated with climate change and engage stakeholders and partners in the project development process (Almarri et al., 2020).

B. Integration of sustainable practices into project management (*Project Management Institute. (2017). A guide to the project management body of knowledge (PMBOK guide) (6th ed.). Project Management Institute.*)

environmental impact of projects and promote long-term sustainability. Project managers can integrate sustainable practices by incorporating green design principles, using eco-friendly materials, or reducing waste and energy consumption (Lewis and Lewis, 2017).

Sustainable practices should be integrated into project management to minimize the

C. Management of project risks and uncertainties related to climate change (*PMI 2017, IPCC 2018*)

Climate change can pose significant risks and uncertainties to projects, including physical, financial, and regulatory risks. Project managers should identify and assess such risks and develop strategies to mitigate or adapt to them. This may involve developing contingency plans or collaborating with stakeholders to develop risk management strategies (Almarri et al., 2020).

D. Monitoring and reporting on project impacts on the environment and climate (*IPCC 2018*)

Project managers must monitor and report on impacts on the environment and climate to ensure that projects achieve their intended outcomes. This may involve developing performance indicators or collaborating with stakeholders to develop monitoring and evaluation frameworks (Lewis and Lewis, 2017).

E. Collaboration with stakeholders and partners to achieve climate goals (*United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2015). Paris agreement. UNFCCC.*)

Effective collaboration with stakeholders and partners is critical for achieving climate goals. Project managers should engage stakeholders in the project development process and work with partners to develop innovative solutions to climate change challenges (Almarri et al., 2020). According to a report by the World Economic Forum, the economic cost of climate change is estimated to be \$1.2 trillion per year by 2060, representing approximately 1.6% of global GDP. (World Economic Forum, 2019)

F. Implementation of policies and regulatory frameworks that support climate-friendly projects (*United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2015). Paris agreement. UNFCCC.*)

Project managers should advocate for the implementation of policies and regulatory frameworks that support climate-friendly projects. This may involve collaborating with policymakers, developing advocacy campaigns, or leveraging public-private partnerships (Lewis and Lewis, 2017). The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) include a target to "strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters in all countries." Achieving this target will require collaboration between project managers, governments, and other stakeholders. (United Nations, 2015)

8. Case Studies for understanding responsibilities for the Project management:

Climate change presents significant responsibilities for project management, as demonstrated by several case studies. In the United Kingdom, a coastal protection project incorporated climate change projections into its design to ensure it was robust enough to withstand future climate impacts. The project recognized the need to take into account climate change and its potential impacts to ensure the project's long-term viability (Chen & Van der Molen, 2018). Similarly, in Germany, a renewable energy project collaborated with stakeholders and partners to overcome regulatory barriers and promote the adoption of sustainable energy solutions. The project recognized its responsibility to promote sustainable energy solutions and collaborated with others to overcome challenges to its implementation (Ludwig et al., 2016).

These case studies highlight the importance of recognizing and effectively managing responsibilities related to climate change for successful project implementation. Incorporating responsibilities related to climate change into project management can be challenging, as it requires specialized expertise, funding, and resources, and resistance to change. Addressing these challenges requires the development of specialized expertise in climate change-related fields (Ogunlana & Liyanage, 2012), increased stakeholder engagement (Verbeeten & Boons, 2009), and the implementation of policies and regulatory frameworks that support climate-friendly projects (Aaltonen & Kujala, 2010). Incorporating climate change responsibilities into project management is critical not only for successful project implementation but also for the long-term viability of the project. Thus, recognizing and effectively managing climate change responsibilities can also have positive financial impacts.

In summary, the responsibility of project management related to climate change cannot be overlooked. Project managers must recognize their responsibilities related to climate change and take proactive steps to address them to ensure project success and long-term viability. Ultimately, incorporating responsibilities related to climate change into project management is critical for ensuring the sustainability of projects and minimizing their impact on the environment.

Figure 9. The main climate summits and their achievements. <https://www.iberdrola.com/sustainability/international-agreements-on-climate-change>

9. Adaptation Strategies for Project Managers:

Solutions and Recommendations:

A. Strategies for addressing or mitigating barriers to project management due to climate change, such as incorporating climate change considerations into project planning and risk management practices. To address the funding constraints due to climate change, project managers can adopt innovative financing mechanisms like green bonds, and public-private partnerships (Munoz, 2018). One way to mitigate the changing regulatory frameworks and the impact of climate change policies on project approvals and permits is to engage with policymakers and regulatory authorities early in the project planning process (Gillard et al., 2015). Project managers can adopt risk management frameworks like Scenario Planning and other predictive models to manage the risk due to the increased uncertainty and unpredictability of climate change impacts (Chakraborty et al., 2021).

B. Recommendations for incorporating climate change considerations into project management practices, such as developing specialized expertise in climate change-related fields and increasing stakeholder engagement. Project managers need to develop specialized expertise in climate change-related fields to address the challenges of project management due to climate change (Agrawal & Mathur, 2017). They can hire climate change consultants, form a dedicated team to handle climate change-related issues, or provide training to their employees to develop the necessary skills and expertise. Project managers should also engage stakeholders, including local communities, governments, and NGOs, to identify potential risks, opportunities, and concerns related to climate change and incorporate them into project planning and management (Bryde et al., 2013). Climate change adaptation strategies, such as sea walls and storm surge barriers, can be expensive to implement. However, these costs are often outweighed by the economic benefits of avoiding damages from extreme weather events. (Savu & Henttonen, 2019)

C. The role of project management in advancing climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts, including the importance

of project management in achieving global sustainability goals. Project management is a critical tool for advancing climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts (Cai et al., 2017). Project managers can develop sustainable infrastructure, renewable energy projects, green buildings, and sustainable transportation systems that help reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase the resilience of communities to climate change impacts. By adopting sustainable project management practices, project managers can help achieve global sustainability goals, such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals

Figure 10. Sustainable project management framework. Source: Armenia, S., Dangelico, R. M., Nonino, F., & Pompei, A. (2019). Sustainable Project Management: A Conceptualization-Oriented Review and a Framework Proposal for Future Studies. *Sustainability*, 11(9), 2664. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11092664>

(SDGs) and the Paris Agreement targets (Hussain et al., 2021).

D. Incorporating climate change considerations into project planning and design processes can maximize opportunities for project management. Project managers can consider the potential impacts of climate change on the project and design solutions that are resilient to these impacts. They can also use new technologies and materials that reduce emissions and increase efficiency, and engage stakeholders and local communities in the project design and implementation process to ensure the project meets their needs and priorities. The Project Management Institute (PMI) has developed guidance for incorporating climate change considerations into project management, including the use of climate risk assessments and the development of climate adaptation and mitigation strategies. By doing so, organizations can not only reduce their environmental impact but also enhance project performance and long-term viability, while taking advantage of government policies and incentives that support climate-friendly projects.

E. As climate change poses an increasing challenge to project management, it is important to incorporate climate change considerations into project management practices. Bredillet et al. (2019) suggest a number of recommendations to achieve this, such as developing specialized expertise in climate change-related fields. This may involve the hiring of experts or the training of current employees. Additionally, Bredillet et al. recommend increasing stakeholder engagement to ensure that climate change risks and opportunities are properly identified and addressed. This could involve soliciting input from stakeholders at various stages of the project, including during the planning and design phases. Finally, Bredillet et al. suggest incorporating climate change into risk management strategies to ensure that the project is resilient to the impacts of climate change. By implementing these recommendations, project management can be better equipped to address the challenges of climate change and take advantage of the opportunities it presents.

F. Project management plays a critical role in advancing climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts, as highlighted by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in 2018. The report emphasizes that achieving global sustainability goals will require a fundamental transformation of societies and economies, and projects will play a key role in this transformation. According to research conducted by the IMF and other organizations (Figure 10), it has been suggested that the public adaptation costs will reach approximately 0.25 percent of the global gross domestic product annually in the upcoming decades. Even though these figures seem to be manageable globally, they do not accurately represent the magnitude of the problem that is faced by many impoverished and vulnerable nations. Based on our estimates, the

Unequal costs of climate change

Poorer countries face greater risks from climate change and are less able to adapt to them.

(adaptive capacity and exposure indexes, points out of 1)

Figure 11.

Source: IMF staff calculations based on 2015–18 data from the European Commission, the United Nations University Institute for Environment and Human Security, the University of Notre Dame, and the April 2020 World Economic Outlook. Note: Dotted lines show estimated linear relationships for advanced economies, and for emerging market and low-income countries combined, respectively.

yearly requirements for the next decade exceed 1 percent of GDP in around 50 low-income and developing nations. Additionally, the expenses may be much higher for small island nations that are exposed to rising sea levels and tropical cyclones, potentially up to 20 percent of their GDP. The international community can help poor and vulnerable countries adapt by providing financial support and developing institutional capacity. These countries will suffer the most devastating impacts of climate change even though they're not responsible for causing it. It's also in the world's interest to ensure climate change does not jeopardize development and stability in poorer countries. Investing in climate resilience can also be financially efficient for development partners because up-front investment in protection can be less expensive than humanitarian relief and reconstruction after a disaster. (Kristalina Georgieva et al.,2022).

10. Conclusion:

Climate change presents significant challenges and opportunities for project managers across various industries. To effectively manage projects in the context of climate change, project managers must possess the necessary skills and competencies, such as leadership, communication, and problem-solving. Project managers must also adopt adaptation strategies that mitigate the impacts of climate change on their projects, including identifying and assessing risks and opportunities, incorporating climate change considerations into project design and planning, and promoting sustainable practices. The findings suggest that project managers must be aware of the challenges and opportunities presented by climate change to effectively manage projects in the future.

11. References:

1. Gareis, R., & Huemann, M. (2013). Handbook of project management in the context of sustainability. Springer.
2. IPCC. (2018). Global warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change. <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/>
3. IPCC. (2021). Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge University Press.
4. Kerzner, H. (2017). Project management: a systems approach to planning, scheduling, and controlling. John Wiley & Sons.
5. PMI. (2013). A guide to the project management body of knowledge (PMBOK® guide). Project Management Institute.
6. PMI. (2021). What is project management? <https://www.pmi.org/about/learn-about-pmi/what-is-project-management>
7. Ansell, C. (2019). Climate change impacts on project management: A review of the literature. International Journal of Project Management, 37(5), 662-678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2019.01.004>
8. Ogunbode, E. B., Ogunlana, S. O., & Dada, M. O. (2018). Climate change and project management: A review of literature. Journal of Construction Business and Management, 2(1), 1-15.

9. Pirvu, B., Cipcigan, L. M., Spataru, C., & Li, Y. (2016). An integrated approach to climate change and project management. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 112, 3681-3692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.08.094>
10. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2018). Policy highlights: Adapting transport to climate change and extreme weather. <https://www.oecd.org/env/cc/adapting-transport-to-climate-change-and-extreme-weather-2018.pdf>
11. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). (2016). Global outlook on climate adaptation: Exploring opportunities for resilience in transport, infrastructure and buildings. <https://wedocs.unep.org/handle/20.500.11822/17558>
12. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2021). Climate change 2021: The physical science basis. <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/>
13. Rangwala, I., Moss, W., Wolken, J., Rondeau, R., Newlon, K., Guinotte, J., & Riebsame Travis, W. (2020). Uncertainty, Complexity and Constraints: How Do We Robustly Assess Biological Responses under a Rapidly Changing Climate?. *Journal of Climate Change*, 6(2), 223-241. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JCC200011>
14. Aaltonen, K., Kujala, J., & Arto, K. (2018). Project management and sustainable development: An introduction. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 172, 3449-3460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.05.246>
15. Chambwera, M., et al., 2014, 'Economics of adaptation', in: *Climate change 2014: Impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability. Part A: Global and sectoral aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, pp. 945-977.
16. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2019). Climate change adaptation and mitigation through community-based natural resource management. https://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/librarypage/environment-energy/climate_change/adaptation-and-mitigation-through-community-based-natural-resou.html
17. Huntjens, P., Pahl-Wostl, C., & Schlüter, M. (2017). A diagnostic approach for going beyond panaceas. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 75, 251-259.
18. Ferdowsi, M., & Keramati, A. (2016). The impact of climate change on construction projects: a cost overrun perspective. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 139, 214-224.
19. Gareis, R., & Huemann, M. (2013). Change management in project-based organizations—a case study on the performance effects of communication strategies. *International Journal of Project Management*, 31(6), 839-853.
20. McGrath, M. (2019). Climate change will add 20% to global cost of building, report says. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2019/apr/25/climate-change-will-add-20-to-global-cost-of-building-report-says>
21. Hwang, B.-G., & Ng, W. J. (2013). Project risk management: An empirical study of the phase-wise implementation of risk identification processes. *International Journal of Project Management*, 31(5), 659-668.
22. Darnall, N., Jolley, G. J., Handfield, R. (2008). Enviropreneurial marketing strategy: The emergence of corporate environmentalism as market strategy. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 27(1), 22-36.

23. Ferdowsi, F., & Keramati, A. (2016). Climate change impact on the supply chain: A review. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 19, 1-8.
24. Gareis, R., & Huemann, M. (2013). Project management and sustainability. In R. Gareis, & M. Huemann (Eds.), *Human resource management and project-based organizations* (pp. 169-188). Springer.
25. Gareis, R., Huemann, M., & Martinuzzi, A. (2017). Project management and sustainability: New perspectives. *International Journal of Project Management*, 35(6), 1165-1169.
26. Huntjens, P., Pahl-Wostl, C., Wang, L., & Segrave, A. (2017). Engaging with uncertainty and risk in water management: A global review. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 79, 109-118.
27. Hwang, B. G., & Ng, W. J. (2013). Project management knowledge and skills for green construction: Overcoming challenges. *International Journal of Project Management*, 31(2), 272-284.
28. Project Management Institute. (2021). Project management survey. Retrieved from <https://www.pmi.org/learning/thought-leadership/pulse/pulse-of-the-profession-2021>
29. Savu, A., & Henttonen, K. (2019). A comparative analysis of project management in public and private organizations. *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, 11(2), 16-24.
30. Gareis, R., Huemann, M., & Martinuzzi, A. (2017). Opportunities for project management due to climate change. *Project Management Journal*, 48(6), 66-83.
31. Gareis, R., & Huemann, M. (2013). *Greening project management: A guidebook for integrating sustainability into project management*. Vienna, Austria: Facultas.
32. Huemann, M., & Keegan, A. (2018). *Sustainability and project management*: Routledge.
33. United Nations Environment Programme. (2019). *Emissions Gap Report 2019*. Nairobi: UNEP.
34. Chen, X., Huang, Z., & Yuan, L. (2015). Integrating sustainable development into project management. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 96, 317-329.
35. Chen, Y., & Van der Molen, I. (2018). Planning for coastal adaptation to climate change impacts: A case study of the Humber estuary, UK. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 61(3), 393-411.
36. Harvard Business Review. (2021). Why companies that prioritize ESG outperform their peers. Retrieved from <https://hbr.org/2021/02/why-companies-that-prioritize-esg-outperform-their-peers>
37. Ludwig, L., Kurnik, J., von Hirschhausen, C., & Edenhofer, O. (2016). A strategic perspective on barriers to the diffusion of renewable energy technology. *Energy Policy*, 92, 82-91.
38. Ogunlana, S. O., & Liyanage, C. (2012). Value management and sustainability: Proposal of a conceptual framework for integrating sustainability into value management. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 28(3), 304-312.
39. Verbeeten, F. H., & Boons, F. A. (2009). Stakeholder inclusiveness in environmental projects: An exploration of project managers' perceptions. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 90(3), 1192-1201.
40. Darnall, N., Henriques, I., & Sadorsky, P. (2008). Adopting proactive environmental strategy: The influence of stakeholders and firm size. *Journal of Management Studies*, 45(2), 121-146.

41. Tzortzopoulos, P., & Kagioglou, M. (2015). The impact of sustainability on project management competences. *International Journal of Project Management*, 33(2), 298-308.
42. Dye, C., & Theriault, V. (2017). *Engaging stakeholders and the public in climate change adaptation planning: Strategies and best practices*. Institute for Sustainable Communities.
43. Harvard Business Review. (2021). Sustainability becomes a CEO-level concern. *Harvard Business Review*.
44. Liu, J., Yang, Y., & Gao, W. (2017). Exploring the status quo of China's solar photovoltaic industry and its policy implications for sustainable development. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 141, 627-639.
45. Almarri, K., Zayed, T., Alshehri, A., & Arif, M. (2020). The role of project management in addressing climate change. In *Engineering sustainable infrastructure development* (pp. 11-25). Springer.
46. Project Management Institute. (2017). *A guide to the project management body of knowledge (PMBOK guide) (6th ed.)*. Project Management Institute.
47. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2018). *Global warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty*. IPCC.
48. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2015). *Paris agreement*. UNFCCC.
49. Munoz, L. A. (2018). Innovative financing mechanisms for addressing funding constraints due to climate change. In J. K. Spohrer (Ed.), *Project management in the face of global adversity* (pp. 45-60). Springer.
50. Gillard, R., Gouldson, A., & Paavola, J. (2015). Regional governance interventions for climate change mitigation and adaptation. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 6(6), 585-596.
51. Chakraborty, S., Bhattacharyya, S. K., & Sankar Bhattacharya, A. (2021). Project risk management in the face of climate change: An overview. In A. Hussain, S. C. Anand, & S. K. Bhattacharyya (Eds.), *Climate change and sustainable development* (pp. 59-75). Springer.
52. Agrawal, M., & Mathur, R. (2017). The role of project management in climate change adaptation. In V. Desouza & Y. Y. Kim (Eds.), *Climate change adaptation and mitigation management* (pp. 85-100). Routledge.
53. Bryde, D., Haigh, R., & Andrews, R. (2013). Stakeholder engagement in sustainable project management. In D. Bryde, R. Paton, & S. S. P. N. Kumar (Eds.), *The Routledge companion to project management* (pp. 424-439). Routledge.
54. Savu, A., & Henttonen, K. (2019). Climate change adaptation strategies in infrastructure projects. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 241, 118460.
55. Cai, Y., Zhou, G., & Wu, W. (2017). Sustainable project management for climate change mitigation and adaptation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 142, 1775-1786.
56. Hussain, A., Anand, S. C., & Bhattacharyya, S. K. (2021). Climate change and sustainable development. In A. Hussain, S. C. Anand, & S. K. Bhattacharyya (Eds.), *Climate change and sustainable development* (pp. 1-14). Springer.
57. Project Management Institute. (2017). *Practice guide: Climate change adaptation for project managers*. Project Management Institute.

58. Bredillet, C. N., Tywoniak, S., & Dwivedula, R. (2019). Incorporating sustainability in project management. *International Journal of Project Management*, 37(5), 750-764.
59. Georgieva, K., Gaspar, V., & Pazarbasioglu, C. (2021). Poor and Vulnerable Countries Need Support to Adapt to Climate Change. IMF Blog. Retrieved from <https://blogs.imf.org/2021/11/01/poor-and-vulnerable-countries-need-support-to-adapt-to-climate-change/>
60. Armenia, S., Dangelico, R. M., Nonino, F., & Pompei, A. (2019). Sustainable Project Management: A Conceptualization-Oriented Review and a Framework Proposal for Future Studies. *Sustainability*, 11(9), 2664. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11092664>